

GRID MATCHING TOOL

Enabling the interaction between georeferenced grid models

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<https://gitlab.com/dlr-ve-esy>

Grid Matching: Identification of clusters of nodes between two grid models

Method to match grids A and B:

- Let $f: A \rightarrow B$ assign to each node in A the closest node in B (using the Euclidean distance) and $g: B \rightarrow A$ vice versa.
- Nodes $a = g(f(a))$ in A are in one-to-one correspondence with nodes $b = f(g(b))$ in B. They are the **centers** of the clusters.
- The rest of the nodes are assigned to a center using the shortest path in each grid.

Clusters in eTraGo German power grid.

Clusters in PyPSA-EUR German power grid.

Comparison of data between different grid models

PyPSA-EUR wind onshore installed capacity in Germany.

eTraGo wind onshore installed capacity in Germany.

PyPSA-EUR grid topology. In red the lines missing in eTraGo.

Transfer of data between grid models

eTraGo grid in Germany.

PyPSA-EUR PV installed capacity in Germany.

PV installed capacity from PyPSA-EUR transferred to eTraGo.

Join two grid models using the clusters with higher resolution parts from each one

eTraGo grid.

PyPSA-EUR grid.

Joined eTraGo and PyPSA-EUR grid.

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[PyPSA-EUR] <https://zenodo.org/record/7646728>

[eTraGo] <https://github.com/openego/eTraGo/tree/0.8.0>